

EVALUATION OF THERMAL COMFORT IN INSTITUTIONAL BUILDINGS IN NAIROBI: A case study of Britam Towers and KCB Towers in Upper hill.

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SDG 11: Sustainable cities and communities/**A-2063 G7:** Environmentally sustainable and climate resilient economies and communities.

SDG 11 Theme: Inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable cities and human settlements/ **A-2063 G7 Theme:** Climate resilience and natural disasters preparedness.

Sub theme: Thermal comfort: A bio climatic approach to sustainability in sub-tropical highland climates.

BIOGRAPHY:

Peter is an award-winning graduate architect from the Department of Architecture and Interior Design (DAID),at Kenyatta University. He has won several awards including the AAK design competition on climate-responsive school design (2021) and the Crown Paints Award of Excellence (2021). Peter also contributed entries for the Norman Foster Foundation workshop (2022), African Union of Architects awards(2024),Kounkey Design Initiative (2023), and the Kahuhia Girls' School dorm design winning entry (2022). He served as an academic secretary of the Architecture Students Association and his architectural research interests include environmental design, health care, and humanitarian architecture. He aspires to pursue further studies in this field.

ABSTRACT:

Climate change is a pressing global concern, particularly impacting tropical regions where rising temperatures pose significant challenges to society, economic well-being, and the built environment. High-rise buildings, that are prevalent in rapidly urbanizing cities like Nairobi, worsen these challenges. This necessitates the pursuit for sustainable design solutions. This research resonated with broader efforts to address challenges of climate change, promoting sustainable urban development. Extensive literature review to this effect highlighted the importance of responding to local climatic conditions in architectural design to mitigate climate change impacts. This study focused on thermal comfort in high-rise buildings in Nairobi, situated within a subtropical highland climate. A general absence of updated information on local precedence for appropriate design that was noted in existing literature, was addressed by exploring Nairobi's unique climatic conditions, and the influence of high-rise structures on thermal conditions for occupants. By bridging the gap between theory and practice, knowledge in the field was refined. A mixed-method

approach, that blended quantitative and qualitative research approaches was employed. Insights arising out of occupant surveys and interviews of key informants or expert were sought for. In this way comprehensive insights into thermal comfort dynamics of high-rise buildings emerged. Through relevant statistical analysis, time series comparisons, and simulation, the study sought to identify optimal strategies to enhance thermal comfort in institutional buildings. For instance, findings from this study revealed that Britam Towers and KCB Towers exhibited minimal variations in thermal comfort figures with Britam Tower having an average of 24.0°C indoor temperatures and KCB Towers having an average of 24.6°C.

This minimal difference was attributed to the facade shading systems and ventilation strategies such as double skin facade and use of solar fins in both buildings. Equally, Natural ventilation strategies in both towers enhanced air circulation, with KCB Towers (with an average indoor air speed of 0.30 m/s) achieving up to 23.3% improved airflow compared to Britam Towers (with an average indoor air speed of 0.23 m/s), resulting in greater thermal comfort for occupants. These findings inform sustainable design practices, supporting more comfortable and livable urban environments, in Nairobi and similar climatic zones globally. It is necessary to integrate climate-responsive design principles into contemporary architectural discourse and practice. This would facilitate the development of resilient urban spaces capable of mitigating the impacts of climate change.

***KEYWORDS:* Passive cooling strategies, solar heat gain,**